

A STUDY ON EMPLOYEES ATTITUDE TOWARDS TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT AT SESHASAYEE PAPER BOARD LIMITED PALLIPALAYAM

Mrs. Sridevi. D

Assistant professor

Department of Commerce CA

KG College of Arts and Science, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu

ABSTRACT: Training and development play an important role in the effectiveness of organizations and to the experiences of people in work. Training has implications for productivity, health and safety at work and personal development. Statistical tool used in this study was Simple average method and Chi-Square method has been used. The sample size for the study is 250 respondents. This study reveals that the effectiveness of the training and development and attitude of the employee in the Seshasayee paper board limited, Pallipalayam.

Key Words: Training and Development, Effectiveness, attitude towards the employee.

1. Introduction:

Every organization needs to have well trained and experienced people to perform the activities that have to be done. It is necessary to raise the skill levels and increase the versatility and adaptability of employees. Training refers to a planned effort by a company to facilitate employees learning of job related competencies. These competencies include knowledge, skill and behaviors emphasized in training programs and to apply them in their day-to-day activities. Recently it has been acknowledge that to gain a competitive advantage, training has to be involved more than just basic skill development. That is, to use training to gain competitive advantage training should be viewed broadly as a way to create intellectual capital. Intellectual capital includes basic skills i.e. skills needed to perform one's job, advanced skills such as how to use technology to share information with other employees, an understanding of the customer's or manufacturing system and self-motivated creativity.

2. Statement of the problem:

Employees are considered as the most valuable resource of any firm. So they need training to equip their skills or enhance their performance. Some enhancement in employees performance could be found after training when it is compared to his/her performance before training. If there is any deviation between standards and actual training is given, the evaluation of employee's performance helps the organization to know the improvement of the employees and this helps to judge any further training is required.

Management development is aimed at preparing employees for future jobs with the organization or solving organization wide problems concerning, acquiring or sharpening capabilities required performing various tasks and functions associated with their presence or expected future roles.

3. Objectives of the Study:

1. To Study the employee attitude towards training and development at Seshasayee paper board limited, Pallipalayam
2. To evaluate the effectiveness of training programs undergone by the employee.
3. To understand the requirement of training to the employees and offer suggestions to the management for implementing more effective training programs.

4. To determine whether the employees developed new skill, attitudes, etc., through training and have implemented them to perform their work more efficiently.

4. Review of Literature:

Michael Kalichman & Sarah Brown (1998) . In recent years, programs for training in research ethics have become widespread, but very little has been done to assess the effectiveness of this training. Trainees were surveyed to assess the role of ethics training in altering their perceptions about their own standards, or their knowledge of options available to them if faced with ethical problems that might arise in conducting and reporting research. In response to a mailing of 505 anonymous questionnaires, 283 replies were received. Similar to previous studies, perceptions of standards were not significantly affected by hours spent in informal discussions about research ethics, in attending courses on research ethics, or in discussions of case studies. This study emphasizes the need for increased attention to the definition and assessment of the goals of research ethics training.

Alan.H.Ayderson (1990) conducted a study and is reported that training is a process to change employee's behavior at work through the application of learning principles.

Duggal (1986) highlights the role of training and development program in HRD. He says that a training and development program could succeed only with proper support and involvement of the top management.

Hornsby, Gatsby and Wake Deled, conducted a study and it is reported "Training means giving teaching and practice in order to bring to a decided standard of behavior efficiency or physical condition".

Dr. U. Surya Rao (2005) conducted a study on effectiveness of training. The objective of this study, to find out the effectiveness of training program. In this study the researcher found that only those who have studied higher studies and above are able to appreciate the practical utility of the program better than those who are less educated, during face to face interactions, women participants hesitate to respond when compared to male. The researcher suggests that subject content should be improved by adding lots of practical examples, for women separate stream should be conducted involving more women trainers.

P. Chinnadurai (2005) conducted a study on "Training Needs Assessment". The objective of the study is to identify the employees who need training, to determine whether training is the best solution to the problem. In this study the researcher found a step by step approach. The researcher suggests that the step by step approach provides a means of identifying and forecasting possible future skills and knowledge deficiencies.

Prof. R.S.S. Mani (2002) conducted a study on Steps for effective training. In this research the researcher identified various steps like identification, pre-training activities, planning and organizing, designing the module, in-house facility, etc. the researcher concludes that the development of the organization lies in the training of quality.

Martin M.Broadwell (1999) observes that most training programs fail because the people who design them don't ask the right questions. In a way, behavioral objectives represent both contract and promise. The promise to the trainer is that if they do their part, they will go back to work, able to do some specific things that are necessary for them to do their job well.

5. Research Methodology:

The study is a descriptive one. Descriptive research includes surveys and fact-finding enquiries of different kinds. The major purpose of descriptive research is description of the state of affairs as it exists at present. 250 respondents are chosen by the researcher as a representative sample for the conduct of the study.

6. Statistical Tool:

1. Simple Percentage Analysis
2. Weighted Average Method
3. Chi-Square test

7. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

TABLE 1
GENDER OF RESPONDENTS ACCORDING TO GENDER

Education	Frequency	Percentage
Male	200	80
Female	50	20
Total	250	100

Source: Primarydata

INTERPRETATION:

The above table depicts that 80% of the respondents are male and 20% of the respondents are female. Majority of the respondents are “Male”.

TABLE NO: 2

CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS ACCORDING TO EDUCATION

Education	Frequency	Percentage
UG	221	88
PG	39	12
Total	250	100

Source: Primary data

INTERPRETATION

The above table interpret 88% of the respondents are Undergraduates and 12% of the respondents are Post graduates.

Majority of the respondents are UG graduate.

TABLE NO: 3

CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS ACCORDING TO AGE

Age	Frequency	Percentage
Below 20	0	0
21-30	48	19
31-40	82	32
41-50	45	18
Above 50	75	31
Total	250	100

Source: Primary Data

INTERPRETATION

The above table denotes that 19 of the respondents are in the age group 21-30, 32% of the respondents are in the age group 31-40, 18% of the respondents are in the age group 41-50 and 31% of the respondents are in the age group of above 50.

Majority of the respondents are 31-40 age groups.

TABLE NO: 4

THE TRAINER AND TRAINEE RELATIONSHIP

Relationship	Frequency	Percentage
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Very good	86	34
Good	54	22
Neutral	35	14
Bad	40	16
Very bad	35	14
Total	250	100

Source: Primary Data

INTERPRETATION

The above table divulged that 34% said “very good”, 22% of the respondents said “good”, 14% of the respondents were “neutral”, 16% of the respondents said “bad”, and 14% of the respondents said “very bad trainer and trainee relationship”.

Majority of the respondents said “very good”.

WEIGHTED AVERAGE

TABLE NO: 1

SATISFACTION OF THE OBJECTIVE

Category	F	W	Fw
Strongly agree	128	5	640
Agree	82	4	328
Neutral	10	3	30
Disagree	13	2	26
Strongly disagree	17	1	17
Total	250	15	1041

Source: Survey Data

Weighted average = $\frac{\sum fw}{\sum f} = \frac{1041}{250} = 4.164$

$W = \frac{4.164}{5} * 10 = 83\%$

INTERPRETATION

The above table shows that 83% of the respondents are highly satisfied that the objective of the training program matches with the training needs.

TABLE NO: 2

SATISFACTION TOWARDS THE FREQUENCY OF TRAINING

Category	F	W	Fw
Highly satisfied	167	5	835
Satisfied	53	4	212
Neutral	10	3	30
Dissatisfied	20	2	40
Highly dissatisfied	0	1	0
Total	250	15	1117

Source: Survey Data

Weighted average = $\frac{\sum fw}{\sum f} = \frac{1117}{250} = 4.468$

$W = \frac{4.468}{5} * 100 = 89\%$

INTERPRETATION:

The above table shows that 89% of the respondents are highly satisfied with the frequency of the training program.

CHI – SQUARE TEST**Hypothesis Test 1: No. of training programmes and level of satisfaction**

Null hypothesis H₀: There is no relationship between Number of training programmes and level of satisfaction,

Alternative hypothesis H₁: There is relationship between Number of training programmes and level of satisfaction,

TABLE NO: 1**NO.OF TRAINING AND PROGRAMMES LEVEL OF SATISFACTION**

No .of training program attend by the respondent in the organization	Level of satisfaction				Total
	Highly satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied	
1-5	35	8	2	5	50
6-10	46	24	4	6	80
11-15	45	7	1	7	60
16-20	40	10	3	2	55
Above 20	1	4	0	0	5
Total	167	53	10	20	250

Source: Survey Data

CHI SQUARE TEST

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	22.667 ^a	12	.851
Likelihood Ratio	7.889	12	.794
Linear-by-Linear Association	.778	1	.378
N of Valid Cases	250		

INTERPRETATION

From the above table, the level of significance at 5% level is 21.026. The calculated value (22.667) is higher than the table value (21.026). Hence, we reject programmes the null hypothesis. So there is significant relationship between Number of training and level of satisfaction.

Hypothesis Test 2: No. of training programmes and opportunities for skill enhancement

Null hypothesis H₀: There is no relationship between Number of training programmes and opportunities for skill enhancement,

Alternative hypothesis H₁: There is relationship between Number of training programmes and opportunities for skill enhancement,

TABLE NO: 2**NO. OF TRAINING PROGRAMMES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR SKILL ENHANCEMENT**

No. of training program attend by you in the organization	Has your skill enhance after the training program		Total
	Yes	No	
1-5	34	20	50
6-10	62	14	80
11-15	45	15	60
16-20	45	10	55

Above 20	2	3	5
Total	188	62	250

Source: Survey Data

CHI SQUARE TEST

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	10.609 ^a	4	.628
Likelihood Ratio	2.468	4	.650
Linear-by-Linear Association	.355	1	.551
N of Valid Cases	250		

INTERPRETATION

From the above table the level of significance at 5% level is 9.488. The calculated value (10.609) is higher than the table value (9.488). Hence, we reject the null hypothesis. So there is significant relationship between Number of training program attended and skill enhancement of the individuals.

FINDINGS:

- It is found that Majority (80%) of the respondents are “Male”, 88% of the respondents are Undergraduates, 32% of the respondents are in the age 31-40, 66% of the respondents are saying yes for to identifying and 79% of the respondents have said that the organization is responsible for training .
- It is indicated that 51% of the respondents strongly agree that the for clearly match with the training needs and Majority of the respondents have attended 6-10 times.
- It is found Classification of the respondents according to the type, majority (58%) of the respondents are grouping type, 53% of the respondents said training programs are conducted every quarterly, 31% of the respondents said time period of training is “too long” and 65% of the respondents feel the need for extension of the training program.
- It’s refers that 75% of the respondents were able to enhance their skill after the training program, 60% of the respondents are given opportunities to implement the skills learnt through training and 41% of the respondents attended training program to impart knowledge.
- It’s found that 83% of the respondents are highly satisfied that the objective of the training program matches with the training needs , 89% of the respondents are highly satisfied with the frequency of the training program and 82% of the respondents strongly agreed with the procedure of conducting the training program.
- It’s found that Significant relationship between Number of training and level of satisfaction, Significant relationship between Number of training program attended and skill enhancement of the individuals,
- It’s evaluated that significant relationship between type of the training and skill enhancement and significant relationship between Period of training and opportunities for employees the skills learnt and significant relationship between Period of training and opportunities for exercising the new skill set.

SUGGESTIONS:

- Equal emphasis should be given to individual training in order to motivate the employees individually and also to increase the effectiveness of training programs.
- Before training program is implemented, we should make sure that all the least relevant topics are replaced by the most relevant ones thereby eliminating unnecessary phases from the program.
- On an average training programs are mostly conducted on half yearly basis. Conducting training programs frequently may help the employees to update their knowledge and acquire more skills in order to increase their competency level
- More practical examples can be included in the training content so that it increases the co-ordination among the employees and also they learn how to implement those practices in their present job.

- Effective training evaluation system should be implemented for increasing the effectiveness of the training program.
- For those employees who feel that the training program led them to stress, they can be selected and their reasons for this can be identified and certain measures should be taken immediately.
Try to improve the relationship between trainer and trainee.

CONCLUSION

It is estimated that the sales and production of Seshasayee paper board limited will be increased in the future. Due to latest technologies the company may face huge competition in the field. New technologies should be implemented in order to compete with the competitors. This requires the employees to know about the technology developments and their usage in the products manufactured by their company. In order to meet this, the employees should be given more training on soft skills and technology developments.

A training program becomes essential for the purpose of meeting the specific problems of a particular organization arising out of the introduction of new techniques, technology, changes in design, the demands of competitions and economy, the quality of production or customer service, individual adjustments, promotions, career development, personal changes etc. It is important for each person to evaluate his attitude towards work. When the successful people are evaluated, one usually finds they that have the ability to concentrate, to be gracious and to follow through on projects.

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